

**Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming
and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets**

Deliverable D8.6

Second batch of 10 Practice abstracts

DOCUMENT/REPORT/PUBLIC

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Summary

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PERSON IN CHARGE	Ambra De Simone
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VERSION	Version 1

History of Changes

VERSION 0.1	9/12/2025	Boglarka Bozsogi (IFOAM EU)	First draft
VERSION 0.2	11/12/2025	Ambra De Simone (IFOAM EU)	Revisions
VERSION 1	17/12/2025	Ambra De Simone (IFOAM EU)	Submission

Executive Summary

OrganicTargets4EU is a Horizon Europe project dedicated to supporting the European Union's Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies, which aim to have at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land under organic farming and a significant increase in organic aquaculture by 2030.

The project develops a range of possible scenarios for achieving the 25% organic targets and propose possible pathways of change. The socio-economic impacts of reaching the 25% organic target are analysed at two strands:

- Production and Markets: Assess where the increases in organic farmland can be achieved and the socio-economic impact of these increases in primary production, value chains, and markets and the mechanisms that can drive demand for organic food.
- Knowledge and Innovation: Identify opportunities to strengthen advisory services and in-conversion and capacity building, increase and coordinate research and innovation investments for organic farming, and work towards an innovation ecosystem fit for achieving the Farm to Fork Strategy's targets.

This deliverable is part of the **knowledge and innovation** strand of the project aiming to foster the availability of advisory services and capacity building for organic value chain actors. For that, the OrganicTargets4EU project delivers twenty practice abstracts in total under Task 8.3 Content production. The practice abstracts have been produced in two batches of ten each, targeting farmers, advisors, and organic actors with practical recommendations. Deliverable D8.3 [First batch of 10 Practice Abstracts](#) was completed in February 2025.

This deliverable comes from the work of practice partners throughout the project, highlighting some key issues or good practices that came out from interactions with local stakeholders and practitioners. The practice abstracts summarise the results of these consultation and collaboration processes in a user-friendly format.

This is the second batch of ten practice abstracts that highlight a diverse range of topics relevant for the **development of the organic sector** (e.g., conversion, AKIS, cooperatives, public procurement, digitalisation) in the seven focus countries on agriculture (Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Romania), two focus countries on aquaculture (Germany, Greece), in addition to results from WP2 Participatory foresight and scenario analysis.

Practice abstract titles:

- Arable farmers, what does it take to convert in Denmark?
- Assisting an organic cooperative in Romania in its digital transformation journey
- Boosting organics through Alternative Food Networks (AFN)
- Living labs: advice for practitioners to work with researchers
- Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in Austria
- Organic Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) with sea bass/sea bream, shellfish, and seaweed to produce blue food
- Public Funding for Fish Farmers Converting to Organic Aquaculture in Germany
- Seizing the opportunity of collective catering to develop organic production

- Steps for farmers to organic agriculture certification in Germany
- Using Scenario Analysis and Backcasting to Strengthen Organic Food & Farming Strategies

1. Introduction

The objective of practice abstracts is to provide actionable recommendations to practitioners, farmers and advisors, on specific issues related to the development of the organic sector in the focus countries or regions. Practice abstracts hope to enable users to learn from the practical experiences of peers, answer concrete questions, provide good practice examples, and open connections with local AKIS actors.

The [practice abstracts](#) follow the EIP-AGRI common format and will be available on the [OrganicTargets4EU project website](#), [Organic Eprints](#), the [Organic Farm Knowledge](#) platform (with the permalink placed at the bottom of each practice abstract), and the [EU CAP Network](#) website with open access for practitioners and the public.

As put by the EU CAP Network, practice abstracts in the EIP-AGRI common format:

- help projects share their results in an easily understandable way for farmers, foresters, rural communities and others from practice
- foster knowledge flows, and shares project results more widely and at a faster pace
- support the development of project proposals with added value, avoiding duplication of ongoing or completed projects
- facilitate networking by connecting project partners with farmers, foresters and others from practice
- answer to real needs from the field

2. Methodology

OrganicTargets4EU develops a range of possible scenarios for achieving the 25% organic targets and propose possible pathways of change. The socio-economic impacts of reaching the 25% organic target are analysed at two strands:

- **Production and Markets:** Assess where the increases in organic farmland can be achieved and the socio-economic impact of these increases in primary production, value chains, and markets and the mechanisms that can drive demand for organic food.
- **Knowledge and Innovation:** Identify opportunities to strengthen advisory services and in-conversion and capacity building, increase and coordinate research and innovation investments for organic farming, and work towards an innovation ecosystem fit for achieving the Farm to Fork Strategy's targets.

This deliverable is part of the **knowledge and innovation** strand of the project aiming to foster the availability of advisory services and capacity building for organic value chain actors. For that, the OrganicTargets4EU project delivers twenty practice abstracts in total under Task 8.3 Content production. The practice abstracts have been completed in two batches of ten each, targeting farmers, advisors, and organic actors with practical recommendations.

This deliverable comes from the work of practice partners throughout the project, highlighting some key issues or good practices that came out from interactions with local stakeholders and practitioners. The practice abstracts summarise the results of these consultation and collaboration processes in a user-friendly format.

The practice partners from the seven organic agricultural focus countries, the two organic aquaculture focus countries, and WP2 Participatory foresight and scenario analysis authored the second batch of ten practice abstracts. The project coordinator IFOAM Organics Europe coordinated the production of the practice abstracts providing guidelines (0), the 2-page template based on the EIP-AGRI common format (**Figure 1**).

First, practice partners submitted a brief proposal outlining the problem statement, solution statement, and expected benefits. Once the focus issue was discussed and confirmed with the project coordination, practice partners submitted their first draft via SharePoint. The review process by IFOAM EU ensured the recommendations to be feasible and actionable for practitioners. Some practice abstracts disseminate a list of trusted organic AKIS actors to contact in a given country or authorities to contact for the conversion process, essential for farmers who need support in converting to organic or improving their organic practices. Other practice abstracts share good regional practices across the food system—including research and innovation, public procurement, regional food provision, and digitalisation—to be implemented in other relevant contexts.

Left Template (Detailed):

ORGANIC TARGETS 4EU Add logo organization PRACTICE ABSTRACT

((Title of the method/approach (max. 150 characters))

Problem (approx. 150 characters) ((Describe the problem being addressed in 1-2 sentences. Include a reference to economic and/or ecological impact)).	Applicability box Theme ((See Annex for list of themes to choose from, maximum 5)) Keywords ((See Annex for list of keywords to choose from, maximum 5)) Context (e.g. geographical coverage, climatic limitations, other) Application time (If relevant) ((Indicate the time of year/season when the method/practice can be applied)) Required time (If relevant) ((Indicate the amount of time required to implement the practice)) Period of impact (If relevant) ((Indicate the period of time in which an impact is expected)) Equipment (if relevant) ((required machinery, if applicable)) Best in (if relevant) ((Indicate in which type of system/with which method is best practiced))
Solution (approx. 150 characters) ((Describe the presented approach to the solution in 1-2 sentences. Mention under what conditions the practice was developed and tested)).	
Benefits (approx. 150 characters) This practice abstract lists current trusted providers of organic advisory services for farmers in transition to organic in Hungary.	
Practical recommendations (approx. 800 characters) (Describe the step-by-step procedure for proper implementation of the method. Include photos or graphs, if possible and useful.).	

Right Template (Simplified):

ORGANIC TARGETS 4EU PRACTICE ABSTRACT

Insert picture here (formatting will be done by the Organic Farm Knowledge editing team). Make sure you reference the picture in the recommendations ("In Picture 1, you can see" etc.)

((Image caption)). Photo: ((Indicate who took the picture))

Further information

Videos

- Check the following video ((Indicate title, put a hyperlink to the site and underline it)) for further instructions ((Indicate language)).

Further reading

- ((refer to existing technical guides, handbooks etc.))

Weblinks

- Check the Organic Farm Knowledge platform [hyperlink] for more practical recommendations.
- ((refer to other websites))

Other useful links:

-

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

Publisher(s): (Institute name (abbreviation) Address, postal code, city Phone, website)	QR code will be added by the OFK editing team	Review: ((added later by OFK or project editing team)) Permalink: Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/xxx Project info: This practice abstract was elaborated by OrganicTargets4EU / Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-for-Fork Targets Project website: https://organictargets.eu/ © 2024
Author: ((names of the authors))		
Contact: ((e-mail address of the first author))		

Figure 1 Practice Abstract template based on the EIP-AGRI Common Format

2.1 Practice abstract (PA) writing roadmap

The procedure informs about the three steps (draft, revision, and finalisation) and indicates the responsible beneficiary. This process was supplemented with a planned timeline to guide the collaboration and ensure timely submission of the deliverable. Once a partner submitted the draft of a practice abstract, IFOAM EU did a first quality check and revision and sent it back to the authors for the implementation of the requested changes. The review process by IFOAM EU ensured the recommendations are feasible and actionable for practitioners, that the information is clear and concise as well as visually attractive and easy to navigate. This step was repeated several times until the draft is of high-quality content and fulfils all EIP-AGRI and OFK platform eligibility requirements. Below the three steps of the production process:

Step 1: Draft (approx. 14 days from the writing request)

- The coordinator sends the writing request with relative deadlines to the project partners responsible for writing the PA
- The author prepares a draft of the Practice Abstract (PA) in the correct template

Step 2: Revision (approx. 1 month)

- The coordinator reviews the PA for quality, clarity, and compliance with criteria
- Reviewer checks for content eligibility
- Authors implement suggestions

Step 3: Finalisation (within 14 days after revision)

- The coordinator makes a final check, finalises the layout, and sends it to the author for approval.
- The coordinator uploads the PAs to [Organic Eprints](#), [Organic Farm Knowledge](#), and the EU CAP Network for dissemination.

3. First batch of 10 Practice Abstracts

This is the second batch of ten practice abstracts that highlight a diverse range of topics relevant for the **development of the organic sector** (e.g., conversion, AKIS, cooperatives, public procurement, digitalisation) in the seven focus countries on agriculture (Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Romania), two focus countries on aquaculture (Germany, Greece), in addition to results from WP2 Participatory foresight and scenario analysis (Deliverable D2.1 Scenarios for the development of the organic sector (forthcoming)).

This section includes a table of the second batch of practice abstracts, the consortium partner that authored it, and the focus country, as well as the practice abstracts themselves as uploaded individually to the [OrganicTargets4EU project website](#), [Organic Eprints](#), and the [Organic Farm Knowledge](#) platform.

Practice abstract title	Author	Country	Permalink
Arable farmers, what does it take to convert in Denmark?	ICOEL	DK	https://www.organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56507
Assisting an organic cooperative in Romania in its digital transformation journey	Inter-Bio	RO	https://www.organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56509
Boosting organics through Alternative Food Networks (AFN)	CIHEAM Bari	IT	https://www.organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56506
Living labs: advice for practitioners to work with researchers	ÖMKi	HU	https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56494
Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in Austria	LKNO	AT	https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56497
Organic Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) with sea bass/sea bream, shellfish, and seaweed to produce blue food	AUTH	GR	https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56508
Public Funding for Fish Farmers Converting to Organic Aquaculture in Germany	Naturland	DE	https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56493
Seizing the opportunity of collective catering to develop organic production	ITAB	FR	https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56495
Steps for farmers to organic agriculture certification in Germany	Naturland	DE	https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56498
Using Scenario Analysis and Backcasting to Strengthen Organic Food & Farming Strategies	INRAE / UNIVPM	-	https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56496

Table 1 First batch of 10 practice abstracts

4. Conclusion

The second batch of ten practice abstracts from the OrganicTargets4EU project highlight a diverse range of topics relevant for the **development of the organic sector** (e.g., conversion, AKIS, cooperatives, public procurement, digitalisation) in the seven focus countries on agriculture (Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Romania), two focus countries on aquaculture (Germany, Greece), in addition to results from WP2 Participatory foresight and scenario analysis. All materials are accessible free of charge on [OrganicFarmKnowledge](#) and the [OrganicTargets4EU](#) project website.

To learn more about the project, please visit our website, consult the [OrganicTargets4EU](#) website and keep an eye out on further deliverables, publications, and events.

Arable farmers, what does it take to convert in Denmark?

Problem

Organic farming requires specialised knowledge and techniques. The available premiums and subsidies are mostly insufficient to compensate for the extra effort (Figure 1).

Solution

Organic farmers can reduce financial uncertainty by adopting preventive and adaptive management strategies (Table 1).

Benefits

Sufficient premiums, targeted subsidies, and payments for ecosystem services compensate the farmers and maintain a competitive farm income.

Practical recommendations

- Use knowledge and recommendations from experienced advisors or peers to optimise input and fixed costs and overall revenues
- Enhance resilience to uncontrollable production conditions by diversifying crops and varieties
- Combine high-value crops (such as grass clover seed or arable vegetables) with bulk products to balance income and risk
- Identify a yield level that minimises vulnerability to fluctuation in prices or environmental factors
- Align cultivation methods and production ambitions that match reduced input costs through resource-efficient practices and self-sufficiency where possible
- Document increases in biodiversity and nature value with the help of certified advisors, enabling payments or subsidies based on measurable ecosystem values
- Calculate the farm's climate impact to avoid potential penalties or taxes.

Applicability box

Theme

Economic challenges, farm management

Keywords

Costs, farm economics, adaption

Context

Denmark

Table 1: Comparison of organic/conventional farm economics for the high-value crop winter rapeseed, based on Danish advisory tool, farm data online, 2025.

Winter rapeseed, data per ha in DKr						
organic			conventional			
Revenue	yield	price/kg	amount	yield	price/kg	amount
sold seeds	2500 kg	6,7	16725	4600 kg	2,79	12834
subsidy (DK)			870			
sum			17.595			12834
Costs						
seed			-675			-488
manure			-700			-700
cleaning			-161			-322
fertiliser			0			-523
weeds			0			-690
fungi			0			-210
insects			0			-110
growth regulation			0			-175
analysis			0			-125
sum			-1.536			-3.343
machine operations etc.			-5.456			-5.861
total costs			-6.992			-9.204
Result			10.603			3.631

Figure 1: Farm income in 1,000 DKK. for conventional (dark green) and organic (green) arable farms (Data from actual farm accounts, all organic farms and a representative group of conventional farms, based on Danish advisory tool, farm data online, 2025.) Farm results measured in thousands of DKK. per farm, show full-time organic farmers in Denmark earn less than their conventional counterparts. In the past two years, their average income has even been negative, despite receiving modest subsidies for organic production. A more realistic rewarding for their contribution to public goods could help offset these losses.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT

Further information

Further reading

- [How have the farmers been motivated and assisted in turning and staying organic? Innovation Centre for Organic Farming,](#)

Weblinks

- [Organic Summit Presentations](#)
- [Check the Organic Farm Knowledge platform for more practical recommendations.](#)

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

Publisher: Innovationscenter for Økologisk Landbrug P/S, Agro Food Park 26, 8200 Aarhus N, www.icoel.dk

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Permalink: [Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56507](https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56507)

Project info: This practice abstract was elaborated by OrganicTargets4EU / Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets

Project website: <https://organictargets.eu/> © 2025

Assisting an organic cooperative in Romania in its digital transformation journey

Problem

Medium-sized organic farms struggle to adopt digital solutions due to limited technological infrastructure, high cost of investments, and lack of knowledge.

Solution

In Romania, Inter-Bio assists the Bio Cătina farmers cooperative in digital transformation through a digital maturity assessment and drones.

Benefits

Farmers gain improved skills to develop a digitalisation strategic plan, apply for financing, and plan resources.

Practical recommendations

Best practices, recommendations for farmers and advisors:

- Learn to use maturity assessment tools (Figure 1), to develop competencies in the areas of technological radar, to test technological solutions before investing in them (Figure 2), and to access to finance for new technologies. More information and training are available at the [Wallachia eHub for digital transformation](#).
- Use drones to remain competitive, reduce costs, and save time
- Get in touch with a European Digital Innovation Hub to take advantage of their specialised services (for instance, Walachia eHub, member of the [European Digital Innovation Hubs Network](#) (EDIH) network)
- Utilise data management and other IT&C solutions such Customer Relationship Management (CRM) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) in combination with the drones

Applicability box

Theme

Farm management; Farm technology and equipment

Keywords

Digital technology

Context

Romania

Period of impact

Implementation takes 5 years

Equipment

Drones

Best in

Medium to large farms (more than 50 ha)

PRACTICE ABSTRACT

T0 DMA Results

View below the results of the DMA Assessment, taken on 20 June 2024 .

T1 DMA Results

View below the results of the DMA Assessment, taken on 24 March 2025 .

Figure 1 Applying Digital Maturity Assessment, the European tool developed by the EDIH network

Figure 2 Road to investment in drones and CRM tools

Further information

Weblinks

- [Bio Cătina farmers' cooperative homepage](#)
- Check the [Organic Farm Knowledge platform](#) for more practical recommendations.

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

Publisher: Inter-Bio, Eternitatii str. 11a, Breaza, Prahova county, Romania, <https://inter-bio.ro/ro/prima-pagina/>

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Project info: This practice abstract was elaborated by OrganicTargets4EU / Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets

Project website: <https://organictargets.eu/> © 2025

Boosting organics through Alternative Food Networks (AFN)

Problem

Despite Common Agricultural Policy support, many farmers remain reluctant to convert to organic farming due to administrative, technical, and market reasons.

Solution

Associating organic practices, values, and products to Alternative Food Networks (AFN)

Benefits

Networks foster synergies across like-minded actors with complementary interests and capacities, which can promote organic conversion.

Practical recommendations

- **Organic advisors should encourage farmer-to-farmer technical exchanges** with experienced organic farmers sharing knowledge.
- **Organic advisory services should provide farmers regular opportunities to meet with experts** to broaden their horizons, get information on organic certification, landraces protection and enhancement, and healthy diets.
- **Organic Alternative Food Networks should organise regular and occasional market initiatives**, such as farmers' markets, local fairs, to foster consumer-producer relations and farmer collaboration.
- **Organic Alternative Food Networks should promote local products through experiential tourism & cultural events** such as heritage & landscape walks, art festivals, tasting events, bike tours, fostering organics as an added value for citizens and tourists.
- **Members of Organic Alternative Food Networks should engage in partnerships** in multi-actor projects (EU, national, local).

Applicability box

Theme

Environment and society, Sustainable communities

Keywords

Organic alliances

Context

Italy

Figure 1 CoP final event flyer

Figure 2: Ostuni medieval peri-urban gardens

Figure 3: Harvesting Violetta aubergine in the gardens

Further information

Further reading

- [Analysis of barriers of conversion and recommendations for strengthening organic advisory services and capacity building, OrganicTargets4EU Deliverable D5.2, 2025.](#) Padel, S., Kunya, Z., Lampkin, N., Jonasz, G., & Szépkuthy, S., ÖMKI.

Weblinks

- [Giardini della Grata: Discover Ostuni's ancient gardens](#)
- [Melanzana Violetta di Ostuni, SlowFood](#)
- [BiodiverSO Puglia](#)
- [Organic Farm Knowledge platform](#)

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

Publisher(s): CIHEAM Bari – via Ceglie 9 – 70010 Valenzano (Bari), Italy, www.iamb.ciheam.org
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Permalink: [Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56506](https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/56506)

Project info: This practice abstract was elaborated by OrganicTargets4EU / Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets

Project website: <https://organictargets.eu/>©2025

Living Labs: a chance for practitioners to work with researchers

Problem

Organic farming and agricultural research remain disconnected; knowledge gaps persist, leaving practitioners without solutions tailored to real farm conditions.

Solution

Living Labs (Figure 1) link organic farmers and researchers to co-create knowledge. They test innovation on farms, adapting to local soil, climate, and management conditions.

Benefits

Joint learning improves practices, builds trust, strengthens resilience, sustainability, and innovation. Farmers act as **co-creators**, ensuring **results are useful**.

Practical recommendations

For Farmers

- Plan time for coordination – treat meetings as part of the learning process, not as extra work.
- Agree early on roles, data-sharing rules, and expected outcomes.
- Start small: test new practices on limited plots before scaling up.
- Build trust through transparency – share both successes and failures.
- Use advisors or facilitators to translate between research and practice.
- Include no-treatment plots and document experiences, so benefits become visible to all partners.

Good practices for farmers, advisors and researchers:

- Engage actively from the start: co-define goals and on-farm experiments.
- Keep transparent records and share practical results, even when outcomes are mixed.
- Dedicate time for reflection with peers and researchers.
- View Living Labs as long-term learning, not just short projects.

Living Labs are rooted directly on farms and must always be adapted to the site-specific context of each farm.

Applicability box

Theme

Environment and society

Keywords

Environment; Society; Living Lab

Figure 1: Example of an organic Living Lab (Source: Dóra Drexler, ÖMKi)

Further information

Further reading

- [Organic living labs and lighthouse farms in Europe](#), 2022, Jonasz, G. & Varga, K., TP Organics
- [Farmers Guide to conducting On-farm Research](#), Orozco, J., P., Hathaway, M., Velez, T., Estrada, H., & Tobey, E. Organic Farming Research Foundation
- [Participatory Research in Organic Farming: Insights from an Agroecology Living Lab in a Mediterranean Area](#), 2024, Colombo, L., Ciaccia, C., Ritunnano, V., Fiore, A., Diacono, M., & Canali, S., Journal of Innovation Management.
- [Harnessing the Potential of Living Labs in European Research Projects on Agriculture. The Case of Promoting Prudent Use of Antimicrobials in Livestock](#), 2024, Oehen, B., Spaans, A., Bonnet-Beaugrand, F., Fortané, N., Kongsted, H., & Vaarst, M., EuroChoices

Videos

- [PERILBIO: Living labs, research and innovation in poultry and aquaculture](#)

Weblinks

- [European Network of Living Labs](#)
- Check the [Organic Farm Knowledge platform](#) for more practical recommendations.

Ökológiai Mezőgazdasági Kutatóintézet
Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
Forschungsinstitut für biologischen Landbau

PRACTICE ABSTRACT

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

Publisher: ÖMKi – Research Institute of Organic Agriculture, Ráby Mátyás utca 26, Budapest 1038, <http://www.biokutatas.hu/>

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Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in Austria

Problem

Communication gaps, fragmented structures, and limited collaboration often prevent research results from reaching organic farmers effectively.

Solution

Interaction between research and farmers can be improved with EIP-AGRI operational groups, Living Labs, advisory networks, and digital knowledge platforms.

Applicability box

Theme

Environment and society

Keywords

Society

Context

Austria

Benefits

Knowledge transfer becomes more dynamic, and research results are accessible for practitioners.

Practical recommendations

Practical instruments and approaches of the Austrian AKIS strengthen knowledge exchange and innovation in organic farming and rural development. Austrian organic farmers can get involved in the below (Table 1) initiatives and take an active role in fostering collaboration between research and practice.

Table 1

Structure	Objectives
EIP-AGRI (European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability) and Operational Groups	
<p>In each call for projects, there is a special budget specifically for organic farming.</p> <p>It brings together farmers, researchers, advisors, and agribusinesses in so-called Operational Groups (OGs).</p>	<p>These groups work on practical, problem-oriented projects, addressing challenges such as soil health, climate adaptation, resource efficiency, or digitalisation.</p> <p>The goal is to co-create and test innovative solutions directly in practice.</p>
AKIS Coordination Office and Thematic Networks	
<p>Since 2023, the AKIS Coordination Office, hosted by Zukunftsraum Land in cooperation with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture (BML) and the Chamber of Agriculture, has been working to enhance networking across sectors. There is a special map of the key actors of the Austrian organic AKIS.</p>	<p>Its mission is to connect research, advisory services, education, and practice more effectively.</p> <p>It develops “Communities of Practice”, where stakeholders collaborate and exchange knowledge on specific topics.</p>
Living Labs and Demonstration Farms	
<p>New methodological formats are gaining importance in Austria to bring science directly to the field.</p>	<p>Living Labs serve as open, real-life environments where farmers and researchers co-develop and test innovations together.</p> <p>Demonstration farms showcase practical applications of research results and new technologies to other farmers.</p>

Advisory Networks and Training for Researchers

Another key strategy is to train both advisors and researchers to work more effectively across the research–practice boundary. Most of the projects in this context are specifically for organic farming.

Projects can strengthen advisors' innovation and communication skills, enabling them to act as "innovation brokers" between farmers and scientists.

Universities and research institutions, such as BOKU Vienna and HBLFA Raumberg-Gumpenstein, offer training for researchers on participatory and transdisciplinary methods, helping them design projects that address real needs in farming practice.

Digital Platforms and Knowledge Management

Digitalisation plays an increasingly central role in knowledge exchange

National platforms and portals (e.g., LFI online courses, AKIS web portal, Smart Farming platforms) make research results, learning materials, and best practices more accessible with specific categories for organic farming.

Collaboration between the Austrian Chamber of Agriculture, BOKU, LFI, and AMA supports the creation of open-access knowledge systems.

New Communication Formats

Communication is recognised as a crucial factor in bridging the gap between science and practice.

Innovation forums, speed-dating events like "Quo vadis AKIS?", and interactive workshops foster dialogue between researchers, advisors, and farmers.

Podcasts, videos, and farmer-led publications share innovation stories and practical experiences in accessible ways.

Further information

Further reading

- [More about EIP Agri Projects in Austria](#)

Videos

- [EIP-AGRI inspirational video: AGRI challenge: soil fertility through carbon storage](#)
- Podcasts [Let's talk about Bio and Farming for Nature](#) focus on organic agriculture and agroecological practices.

Weblinks

- [modernAKIS](#)
- Demonstration farm projects: [modernAKIS](#), [Smart Rural 21](#), [ClimateFarmDemo](#).
- A good example for an organic demonstration farm in Austria is [Grand Farm](#).
- [Projekte - Netzwerk Zukunftsraum Land](#)
- [AKIS-Kooperationsstelle - Netzwerk Zukunftsraum Land](#)
- [Smart Farming: Vielzahl an Angeboten in Österreich | LFI Österreich](#)
- [i2connect - Home - i2connect](#)
- [Organic Advice Network](#)
- Check the [Organic Farm Knowledge platform](#) for more practical recommendations.

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Project website: <https://organictargets.eu/> © 2025

Organic Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) with sea bass/sea bream, shellfish, and seaweed to produce blue food

Problem

Conversion to organic fish farming often requires significant investments, which can be difficult for small and medium-sized farms to finance independently.

Solution

Greek fish farmers can diversify to Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) and certify both the seaweed, shellfish and the sea bream/sea bass organic (Figure 1).

Applicability box

Theme

Animal husbandry, Production systems, Aquaculture

Keywords

Aquaculture

Context

Greece

Benefits

IMTA increases the techno-economic and environmental sustainability of aquaculture and improves the final product quality.

Practical recommendations

- Develop **new reproduction and hatchery protocols** for seedling production of the macroalgae.
- Evaluate the **nutritional profile** of the target species according to the EU-labelling requirements for organic blue food.
- Develop a **conversion and investment plan** aligned with EU organic regulations and national program requirements.
- Secure **support in the transition phase** with a focus on professional and technical areas.
- **Collaborate** and co-create in Living Labs, and on-farm experiments: Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki.
- Locate **organic certification requirements**: Certification bodies (Agrocert, BioHellas, TÜVHellas).
- **Administrative assistance**: mainly in the application process for organic subsidies: Advisors working in the network of Geotechnical Chambers of Agriculture, and independent advisors.

Figure 1. IMTA Farm: multitrophic aquaculture with fish, seaweed, and shellfish.

ΑΡΙΣΤΟΤΕΛΕΙΟ
ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ
ΘΕΣΣΑΛΟΝΙΚΗΣ

PRACTICE ABSTRACT

Further information

Further reading

- [National Strategic Plan on Aquaculture \(GR\)](#)
- [Can IMTA provide added ecosystem value services in the fish farms of Greece? 2023, Papageorgiou, N., Dimitriou, P. D., Chatzivasileiou, D., Tsapakis, M., & Karakassis, I., Frontiers in Marine Science.](#)
- [Changes of the Mediterranean fish farm sector towards a more sustainable approach: A closer look at temporal, spatial and technical shifts. Ocean Coast. 2021, Papageorgiou, N., Dimitriou, P. D., Moraitis, M. L., Massa, F., Fezzardi, D., & Karakassis, I., Science Direct.](#)
- [Is Europe ready for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture? a survey on the perspectives of European farmers and scientists with IMTA experience. 2018, Kleitou, P., Kletou, D., & David, J., Elsevier.](#)

Weblinks

- [Hellenic Aquaculture Producers Organisation](#)
- Check the [Organic Farm Knowledge platform](#) for more practical recommendations.

Other useful links:

- [Ministry of Rural Development and Food](#)
- [Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, School of Veterinary Medicine, Laboratory of Aquaculture and Aquatic Animal diseases](#)
- [Hellenic Centre of Marine Research \(HCMR\)](#)

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Public Funding for Fish Farmers Converting to Organic Aquaculture in Germany

Problem

Conversion to organic fish farming often requires significant investments, which can be difficult for small and medium-sized farms to finance independently.

Solution

Fish farmers in Germany can access a range of public funding instruments (Table 1) to support the transition to organic farming.

Benefits

Access to funding can substantially reduce financial barriers and thus be an incentive for conversion to organic farming.

Applicability box

Theme

Farm management, standards, regulations and certification, animal husbandry, aquaculture

Keywords

Aquaculture, farm economics, costs, conversion factors

Context

Germany

Practical recommendations

- Contact the state fisheries authority (Landesfischereibehörde) or Managing Authority for European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) for information on current funding calls.
- Develop a conversion and investment plan aligned with EU organic regulations and national program requirements. The eligibility & contacts are state-specific.
- Combine investment support with training/consultancy on the organic certification process
- Managing authority is often the state ministry/Landwirtschaftskammer/Landesamt. Contact them to find the correct measure and check whether your project fits the “investment in aquaculture” or “environmental improvement/organic conversion” lines.
- Many states operate rolling applications for certain investment measures; others use discrete funding calls with fixed deadlines. Use the linked state page to confirm the current call and the list of eligible costs.

Table 1: Table of funding contacts & pages by federal state (Germany) – organic aquaculture/conversion relevance

State	Programme / landing page	Managing authority / contact	Deadlines / notes
Schleswig-Holstein	Landesprogramm «Fischerei und Aquakultur 2021–2027» (EMFAF implementation & investment rules). (schleswig-holstein.de)	Responsible: Landesamt für Landwirtschaft & nachhaltige Landentwicklung (LLnL), Dezernat 30 – Fischereiförderung. Contact listed on page (Ines John / Jan-Moritz Grohall). (schleswig-holstein.de)	Many measures: mostly rolling / no fixed deadlines for several measures; some calls have defined cut-offs – check the page. (schleswig-holstein.de)
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	EMFAF / Landesförderung Aquakultur & Fischerei (Regierungsportal M-V). (Regierungsportal M-V)	Managing authority details on site (Ministerium / Ansprechpartner in den Seiten). See linked page. (Regierungsportal M-V)	Programme operational 2021–2027; specific calls & press releases posted on the site (follow call notices). (Förderdatenbank)
Niedersachsen	EMFAF / Binnenfischerei & Aquakultur information (ML Niedersachsen / LWK implementation). (Niedersachsen Ministerium Ernährung)	Umsetzung / Bewilligungsbehörde: Landwirtschaftskammer Niedersachsen (LWK) (since 01.03.2025). See LWK contact pages & LAVES info. (Niedersachsen Ministerium Ernährung)	Several measures available; application forms and guidance via LWK – some measures accept continuous applications, others via announced calls. (agrarfoerderung-niedersachsen.de)
Bremen	EMFAF information / Förderhinweise (Senate / Häfen-Bremen portal). (haefen.bremen.de)	Managing authority details on the Bremen Senate/ports pages (see linked PDF & portal). (Rathaus Bremen)	EMFAF-funds used for targeted measures; check the Bremen portal for current calls. (haefen.bremen.de)
Hamburg	Hamburg – official pages on fisheries / admin; IFB Hamburg handles many EU funds information (see Hamburg pages). (Hamburg.de)	IFB Hamburg and the relevant Hamburg ministry / Bukea pages – see linked contacts on the pages. (IFB Hamburg)	Hamburg handles EU funds via IFB and ministry channels; check IFB / ministry for open calls. (Hamburg.de)
Berlin	EMFAF / joint Berlin-Brandenburg aquaculture directive (see LELF / joint Richtlinie). (MLEUV)	Berlin/Brandenburg scheme: Antrags-/Bewilligungsbehörde is listed in the joint Richtlinie (see LELF/ML). (lelf.brandenburg.de)	Joint Richtlinie (Berlin + Brandenburg) valid (Richtlinie dated 7 May 2024) – follow the LELF page for calls and attachments. (MLEUV)
Brandenburg	Richtlinie zur Förderung der Aquakultur und Binnenfischerei (EMFAF) – LELF / MLEUV. (MLEUV)	Bewilligungsbehörde / Ansprechpartner in der Richtlinie (see linked PDF / LELF page). (lelf.brandenburg.de)	Guidelines runtime shown to 31.12.2029; calls / specifics published on LELF. (MLEUV)
Nordrhein-Westfalen (NRW)	EMFAF implementation pages (MLV & Landwirtschaftskammer NRW): EMFAF-Richtlinie + Förderaufrufe. (Landwirtschaftskammer)	Antragsstelle: Landwirtschaftskammer NRW (formulare & Ansprechpartner listed). Example contact: Claudia Kloß (LWK) referenced on guidance pages. (Landwirtschaftskammer)	NRW publishes specific Förderaufrufe (pdf list). Some measures for aquaculture/processing have fixed application windows – see the MLV pdfs. (MLV NRW)
Hessen	Regional pages: RP Darmstadt – Fischereiförderung / guidance for fishery support. (rp-darmstadt.hessen.de)	Regional authority (Regierungspräsidium / Landesministerium) contacts on the RP-site – see page. (rp-darmstadt.hessen.de)	Programme & rules apply under national EMFAF framework; check RP for deadlines & required forms. (rp-darmstadt.hessen.de)
Rheinland-Pfalz	Landesförderung / Förderprogramme list for Aquakultur & Fischerei (state portal / Förderdatenbank). (RLP Service)	Contact details & procedure are on the state service pages (see linked page). (RLP Service)	Regional calls & innovation funding run under state rules; check the state page for current deadlines. (Förderdatenbank)

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State	Programme / landing page	Managing authority / contact	Deadlines / notes
Saarland	Saarland ministry pages / local fisheries funding information (state portal / MUKMAV guidance). (saarland.de)	See state portal / regional fishery association links for contacts; small local subsidy schemes may exist (contact Landesministerium). (fischereiverband-saar.de)	Many regional payments (e.g., agrar claims) follow national calendar; for aquaculture projects check with state ministry. (saarland.de)
Bayern	EMFAF landing page / Bayern EMFAF information (stmelf / EMFAF Bavaria, application guidance). (s.bayern.de)	Managing authority & LfL / STMELF guidance page – contact info and Merkblatt (application guidance) on the site. (Staatsministerium Bayern)	Bayern shows an application period (e.g., “Antragszeitraum 17.04.2023–31.12.2027” for many measures) and budget information – check the Bayern EMFAF page for current available budget & deadlines. (s.bayern.de)
Baden-Württemberg	Landesförderprogramm «Aquakultur und Fischerei» (FAF-BW guidance & press release for new programme 2023). (Baden-Württemberg.de)	State ministry / FAF-BW implementation office details on the announcement page (see link). (Baden-Württemberg.de)	New programme established (2023); follow ministry pages for calls & eligible measures. (Baden-Württemberg.de)
Thüringen	Thüringer Förderrichtlinie Aquakultur / EMFAF (TMIL / Richtlinie PDF). (umwelt.thueringen.de)	Contact & procedure: Thüringer Ministerium / TMIL (Richtlinie PDF includes Ansprechpartner und Antragsweg). (umwelt.thueringen.de)	Subsidies available for aquaculture / pond farming – typical co-financing rates & deadlines shown in directive; check PDF. (Förderdatenbank)
Sachsen	Förderrichtlinie Aquakultur und Fischerei (FRL AuF/2023) – SAB / Staatsministerium pages. (Sächsisches Amt für Besoldung)	Bewilligungsbehörde und Formularhinweise: SAB / sächsische Richtlinie – contact info on the page. (Sächsisches Amt für Besoldung)	FRL AuF/2023 active – check SAB for specific open calls and program windows. (Förderdatenbank)
Sachsen-Anhalt	Landesverwaltungsamt / Förderschwerpunkte Fischerei & Aquakultur (LVWA pages / Richtlinien). (Landesportal Sachsen-Anhalt)	Ansprechpartner / Förderabteilung: Landesverwaltungsamt (see LVWA page). (Landesportal Sachsen-Anhalt)	See LVWA page for local deadlines; some measures have fixed cut-offs, other funding is open via announced calls. (Landesportal Sachsen-Anhalt)

PRACTICE ABSTRACT

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Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
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Swiss Confederation

Seizing the opportunity of collective catering to develop organic production

Problem

France has a target of 20% organic food catering (Egalim Law¹), but organic farmers struggle due to fragmented supply, unsuitable volumes, and strong logistical constraints.

Solution

Farmers and processors organise their supply collectively, adapt volumes, cooperate with regional food hubs or logistic platforms to meet public procurement requirements.

Applicability box

Theme

Food chain management, Environment and society, Sustainable communities,

Keywords

Agricultural organisations, Sustainability,

Context

France

Benefits

A stable and growing outlet for farmers and processors, organic gains local visibility, and the 20% organic food in both public and private canteens target is reached easier.

Practical recommendations

To supply collective catering in France, organic producers should (Figure 1):

- Organise collectively into cooperatives or producer groups to pool volumes and adapt the format of food containers for public caterers
- Collaborate with local processors to ensure raw products meet catering requirements
- Use local micro-hubs to centralise logistics, facilitate deliveries, and optimise transport
- Establish long-term contracts with caterers to secure stable volumes and prices, enabling production planning and investment
- Advocate for public procurement rules to integrate sustainability and local sourcing criteria
- Align production and supply with the Egalim targets to secure demand for organic products
- Coordinate production and logistics to overcome supply fragmentation and expand organic offerings in collective catering.

¹ The Egalim law has imposed a 20% organic requirement in public catering by 1 January 2022, and in private catering by 1 January 2024. Please note: the Egalim law does not only apply to public procurement.

Seizing the opportunity of collective catering to develop organic production

Figure 1: Cooperation between organic stakeholders to achieve 20% organic food in collective catering

Further information

Further reading

- OrganicTargets4EU Deliverable D4.2 Report on Delphi experts' interviews on value chain changes and business strategies, 2025, IFOAM Organics Europe
 - [English version](#)
 - [French version](#)

Weblinks

- [Organic Targets4EU project website](#)
- Check the [Organic Farm Knowledge platform](#) for more practical recommendations.

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Project website: <https://organictargets.eu/> © 2025

Steps for farmers to organic agriculture certification in Germany

Problem

Farmers in Germany who want to convert to organic production often lack access to relevant information and guidance.

Solution

Provide information to farmers about the basic steps to take for conversion and give an overview of actors that can provide assistance.

Benefits

Enabling farmers to get access to relevant public and private actors and information to support them with conversion to organic farming practices and learning new practices.

Applicability box

Theme

Conversion to organic – standards, regulations, certification and advanced training

Keywords

Conversion, control agency, advisory service, further education

Context

Germany

Practical recommendations

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Further information

Useful contacts (Germany) – advisory services, authorities, certifiers & more

Federal / national authorities & information

- Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) – Organic farming overview / policy
 - Offices in Bonn & Berlin
 - Links: [General Contact](#) & [BMLEH – Controls in Organic Farming](#)
- Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (BLE) – Organic programme pages
 - Bio-Siegel contact: Phone: +49 228 6845-2200 + E-mail: bio-siegel@ble.de.
 - [BLE organic pages](#) for information and resources

Regional advisory / practical farm advice

- Verband der Landwirtschaftskammern ([portal to Regional Chambers](#)) – central directory for all state Chambers of Agriculture to find your state contact; Website/addresses directory: [Map of organic advisory services](#)
- [Ökolandbau.de](#) – [information portal](#)

Approved control bodies

Official list of control bodies (Germany) – central list and downloadable documents: (Ökolandbau portal / BLE). Use this to pick a certifier for your product/region: [Liste Kontrollstellen EU.pdf](#)

Major organic associations & advisory/certification services

- Bioland e.V. (advice, producer support, certification options)
 - Kaiserstr. 18, 55116 Mainz · Phone: +49 6131 23979-0 · E-mail: info@bioland.de; www.bioland.de
- Demeter e. V. (biodynamic standards, certification/advice)
 - Brandschneise 1, 64295 Darmstadt · Phone: +49 6155 84690 · E-mail: info@demeter.de; www.demeter.de
- Naturland e.V. (association + advisory)
 - Kleinhaderner Weg 1, 82166 Gräfelfing · Phone: +49 89 898082-0 · E-mail: naturland@naturland.de; www.naturland.de

Networks & specialist advisory

Organic advisory networks & portals (training and advisor directories) – e.g., Organic-FarmKnowledge / EU organic advisory networks – good to find regional organic advisors and technical publications; www.organic-farmknowledge.org

Weblinks

- Check the [Organic Farm Knowledge platform](#) for more practical recommendations.

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Using Scenario Analysis and Backcasting to Strengthen Organic Food & Farming Strategies

Problem

Organic sector actors often lack structured tools to anticipate future challenges and test long-term strategies.

Solution

Apply scenario analysis and backcasting to identify resilient pathways and align actions with long-term goals.

Benefits

Improved foresight, shared vision, and more adaptive, evidence-based strategies for organic food systems.

Practical recommendations

To test opportunities, threats and strategies, combine **scenario analysis** (aka **scenario planning**, exploring multiple plausible futures) with **backcasting** (building pathways connecting milestones and actions to be implemented to reach a desirable 2040 vision).

- **Co-create scenarios** with farmers, processors, policymakers, and researchers to identify key drivers of change (markets, climate, regulation, technology).
- **Explore impacts** of each scenario on organic farming practices, markets, and value chains.
- **Backcast** from preferred futures to define concrete policy and business steps needed today.
- **Compare options** across scenarios to identify robust strategies that perform well under uncertainty.
- **Integrate results** into regional action plans and CAP Strategic Plans to enhance coherence and resilience.

Applicability box

Theme

Environment and society

Keywords

Society

Context

EU organic sector, applicable at regional and national levels for policy and strategic planning

Application time

Throughout any policy or business planning cycle

Required time

1–3 months for full stakeholder workshop cycle

Period of impact

Medium to long term (3–15 years)

Best in

Multi-actor platforms, policy design groups, advisory services, innovation hubs

Further information

Further reading

- [Scenario Analysis: A Primer](#). The Pentland Centre for Sustainability in Business, 2024, Ciftci N., Bebbington J., Pollard D. The Pentland Centre for Sustainability in Business.
- [Scenarios of the organic food market in Europe](#), 2012, Zanolli, R., Gambelli, D., Vairo, D. *Food Policy*, 37(1), 41-57.
- [A review of scenario planning](#), 2013, Amer, M., Daim, T.U., Jetter, A. *Futures*, 46, 23-40.
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PRACTICE ABSTRACT

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